

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

Deliverable 10

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Hackathon report

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List of Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface

GEE Google Earth Engine

IDE Integrated Development Environment

NDVI Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

PoC Proof of Concept

REST Representational State Transfer

UDF User Defined Function

URW Use Case / User Requirements Workshop

1. Introduction

The openEO Hackathon took place from 25-26.06.2018 in the facilities of TU Wien at the Gusshausstrasse 27-29 in Vienna, Austria. The Hackathon is part of Task 2.2 "Workshops & Hackathons" of work package 2 "User Involvement & Dissemination" of the openEO project. Therefore, the aim of the openEO Hackathon was to get initial feedback from potential users and identify potential strengths and weaknesses. Since that Hackathon was conducted in month 9, early in the openEO projects life cycle, the results enable us to identify bottom-up usability problems and provide a framework for further improvements and adaptations.

This report provides an overview on the methodology, results and achievements of the openEO Hackathon. In section 3 the planning and execution of the Hackathon is explained in further detail. Section 4 lists findings and observations from the Hackathon as well as potential for improvement. An overview of developed implementations by the participants of the Hackathon is given in section 5. Finally, a conclusion on the impact of the Hackathon on openEO is drawn in section 6.

2. Executive Summary

The openEO Hackathon was divided into two main sessions. The first session "Test Cases" was intended to provide feedback from the users, by asking the participants to implement basic tasks, i.e. deriving a minimum NVDI from Sentinel-2 time series using openEO. Another aim of this session was to get a first insight into the openEO clients, back-end drivers and the Core API to leverage the development of ideas in the subsequent session. The "Hacking" session enabled the participants to implement own ideas using openEO or extensions on top of openEO.

By working on the test cases, various usability problems, relating to the installation of the client libraries, creating process graphs or the general handling of openEO were identified. Furthermore, several additional user needs were gathered, like the lack of a graphical access to construct chained processes for novice users. An additional aim of this session was the assessment of the documentation and descriptions of openEO. These tests resulted into the requirement to improve the current documentations, as well as providing further examples on how to use openEO.

The participants subsequently developed multiple solutions, that were connected to the problems identified during the test cases, like the development of a visual process graph builder or implementing own ideas, e.g a client generator to ease the development of various openEO client libraries. Furthermore, multiple improvements and extensions of the openEO Python and R clients were implemented, as well as in advance suggested ideas by the openEO consortium, like a GraphQL endpoint for openEO.

The overall results of the Hackathon will be used to improve the quality of openEO with respect to the user needs and requirements and leverage the further development of the single openEO layers.

3. Planning

The Hackathon was held as a one and a half day event and was jointly organised with the Use Case / User Requirements Workshop (URW). In total 24 participants were registered for the openEO Hackathon, including 5 mentors from the openEO consortium. The URW is derived from the shifting and splitting of the Strategic & Use Case Workshop of the openEO project that was originally planned for M7. The agenda is shown in section 1.1, the results from the URW are reported in D08 (Preliminary User Requirements report).

The purpose of the Hackathon was to test the basic functionality of the openEO clients and the Core API, as well as collecting early feedback from potential users. Furthermore, the participants had the possibility to contribute by implementing own ideas for new functionalities or modifying the existing implementations of openEO. The aims of the event included identifying possible design concerns and potential for improvement. Finally, discussions about strength and weaknesses of the openEO with the participants were conducted to further investigate the collected insights on openEO.

For registration and providing information, a website for the Hackathon was created that can be found at <https://openeo-hackathon.eodc.eu/>.

The results of the Hackathon and the URW will be used to improve the quality of implementation of openEO as well as provide guidance in certain areas of the project.

3.1. Agenda

The agenda of the Hackathon and the URW is shown in the following table. The items that belong to the Use Case / User Requirements Workshop are marked with "URW".

Day 1	
Time	Item
09:00 - 10:00	Registration
10:00 - 10:30	Welcome and Introduction to openEO
10:30 - 12:00	Test Cases
12:00 - 12:45	Lunch
12:45 - 17:00	Hacking
17:00 - 17:30	Day 1 Wrap-Up
17:30 - 18:00	Presentation of openEO User Requirements Survey (URW)
18:00 -	Snacks, Drinks and Networking
Day 2	
09:00 - 13:00	Hacking
13:00 - 14:00	Lunch
14:00 - 14:30	Day 2 Wrap-Up
14:30 - 15:45	Feedback from the Hackathon (URW)
15:45 - 16:00	Raffle and Closing Note

Table 3.1: Agenda of the Hackathon

3.2. Procedure

The event was initiated with an introduction to: the proceedings of the Hackathon, the available clients and back-end drivers, and the design of the openEO Core API. The introduction included detailed technical background of the single layers of openEO, as well as the communication between the clients and the back-ends. The introduction session aimed to provide first insights on openEO to the participants and facilitate the subsequent development processes.

Following the introduction of openEO, the participants were asked to implement multiple tasks, that were intended to provide a deeper insight to openEO and to test the basic functionality. Therefore, the test cases served as basic usability checks and enabled us to get initial feedback from potential users. The attendees could choose between the Python and R Clients to implement the test cases. Furthermore, two back-end drivers (GeoTrellis hosted at VITO and Google Earth Engine (GEE) hosted at WWU) were prepared to provide responses to the requests of the test cases. The participants were encouraged to bring their personal computers and development environments, to guarantee that the test cases were implemented using familiar environments. The test cases are further described in section 3.4 Test Cases.

The first of two hacking session started after the lunch break. The participants were free to work individually or in teams on ideas for applications that are using openEO or extending the existing functionality of the openEO clients, back-end or the Core API. To support the development of creative ideas, some suggestions for possible implementations were provided by the mentors to the attendees (see section 3.5 Hacking). The second hacking session on day 2 enabled the participants to further develop on their projects. The hacking sessions were followed by a short wrap-up, in which each participant presented achievements, opinions and insights on openEO. To leverage the discussions on openEO, a social event was held at the end of day one.

The two URW sessions included the presentation and discussion of the user survey that was conducted by WUR, a SWOT analysis and group discussions on openEO. The user survey presentation and the discussion session were accessible externally via a provided GoToMeeting stream. The aim was to include externals to join the discussions.

The overall event was finished with a closing note and a raffle in which the participants had the possibility to win one of multiple vouchers (provided by EODC).

3.3. Objectives

The overall objective of the Hackathon was to: i) gain a deeper insight from potential users on openEO, and ii) to determine if the design of the openEO Core API and the client implementations facilitate the user's ability to perform routine tasks (test cases).

The specific objectives of the Hackathon are following listed in further detail:

- **User Feedback** - Use the client libraries under controlled test conditions with representative users. Observations and opinions were evaluated to assess whether goals regarding an effective, efficient, and well-received design have been achieved.
- **Finding Usability Problems** - To determine design inconsistencies and usability problem areas within the client libraries or the Core API. Potential sources of error may include:

- **Setup problems** - The users may fail to install and implement the client libraries into existing development environments. Furthermore, the users may not be able to establish to connect the client with a back-end.
- **Comprehension problems** - The users may have problems to understand the objectives or retrieve the capabilities of openEO.
- **Usage problems** - The users may have problems to achieve their tasks or fail to comprehend how to achieve them using openEO.
- **Communication problems** - The structure of requests and responses, as well as the error handling may be an obstacle.
- **Implement Ideas** - The participants had the possibility to actively develop and improve new or current functionalities for the client libraries, to adapt the design of the Core API of openEO or to implement new features on the back-ends.

3.4. Test Cases

The test cases are derived from the use cases that were developed for the demonstration of the Proof-Of-Concept (see [PoC Use Cases](#)). The aims of the test cases were to enable the participants to get a first insight in the setup and use of openEO. Furthermore, the test cases allowed to get first opinions and feedback on the usability of the openEO implementations. The test tasks were mostly covering the basic functionality of the openEO clients and the Core API and were identical for all the Hackathons attendees. The participants were working on the test cases with their personal computers and with their preferred Integrated Development Environment (IDE) / Editors to guarantee that the implementation of the test cases were conducted in a familiar environment. The users joining the Hackathon had the choice to use the Python or R client.

The solutions for the test cases in Python and R can be found at the following sites, with exception for task 5 which is only executable at the GeoPySpark back-end.

- [Solutions for R client with GEE back-end \(tasks 1 - 4\)](#)
- [Solutions for Python client with GEE back-end \(tasks 1 - 4\)](#)
- [Solutions for Python client with GeoPySpark back-end \(tasks 1, 2, 4, 5\)](#)

3.4.1. Task 1: Installation

The aim of Task 1 was to observe, if the users are able to install the clients on their local machines. Furthermore, by requesting the capabilities of the back-end, the users needed to find the corresponding function call of the respective client library in the documentation.

The task is defined as following:

Please install an openEO client of your choice:

- Python client

- R client

Make sure that the client is properly working by connecting to the openEO Earth Engine back-end and requesting the capabilities that are provided by the back-end.

3.4.2. Task 2: Information

The second task was supposed to identify problems in finding products or processes that are available at the back-ends. The participants were tasked to find the corresponding functions to retrieve all products, all processes and detailed information of a product and process.

The task is defined as following:

You want to know which products and processes are offered by the back-end. Please find this information. Furthermore, you want to know which temporal extent is available for a specific product (e.g. Sentinel-2) and which arguments need to be provided for processing the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).

3.4.3. Task 3: Processing

Task3 asked the participants to retrieve maximum NDVI values of single pixels from Sentinel-2 time series. Therefore, the users needed to find the corresponding processes and execute a job on the back-end. Furthermore, the results of the processing should be downloaded as PNG or GeoTiff.

The task is defined as following:

You want to derive maximum NDVI values from pixel values derived from Sentinel-2 time series of Vienna. The extends that you are interested in:

- bounding box (left: 16.138916, top: 48.320647, right: 16.524124, bottom: 48.138600, EPSG:4326)
- temporal extent (01.01.2018 - 31.01.2018)

You want to download the results as PNG (with additional color stretching) or GeoTiff.

3.4.4. Task 4: Zonal Statistics

The objective of task 4 was to observe if the users are able to upload files to their user space and integrate the files in a processing graph. Specifically, a time series of zonal (regional) statistics of Sentinel-2 imagery should be computed using a user-uploaded polygon.

The task is defined as following:

You want to compute time series of zonal statistics (arithmetic mean / average) of Sentinel-2 data using a predefined polygon. First of all you should check if the process `zonal_statistics` is provided by the back-end. Furthermore you need to upload GeoJSON file containing the polygon. Use the following extents and band:

- bounding box (left: 16.138916, top: 48.320647, right: 16.524124, bottom: 48.138600, EPSG:4326)
- temporal extent (01.01.2018 - 31.01.2018)
- band: 8

You want to perform a batch processing and afterwards download the results as JSON.

3.4.5. Task 5: User Defined Functions

For the fifth task the participants had to create a monthly aggregated Sentinel 2 product from a custom Python script. Therefore, a provided Python script had to be uploaded to the back-end and executed by defining a process graph that integrates the user-defined function.

The task is defined as following:

Make sure that the Python client is properly working by connecting to the openEO GeoPyspark back-end and requesting the capabilities that are provided by the back-end. You want to find out which Sentinel-2 data is available at the back-end, as well as if the back-end provides User Defined Functions (UDFs). You want to run the provided Python script on each time series of the data set. The extents are defined by:

- bounding box (left: 6.8371137, top: 50.5647147, right: 6.8566699, bottom: 50.560007, EPSG:4326)
- temporal extent (10.10.2017 - 30.10.2017)

You want to download the results as GeoTiff (GTiff).

3.5. Hacking

The two hacking sessions, with a total duration of around 8 hours, enabled the participants to implement their own ideas using openEO. Therefore, the participants were asked to develop applications that are utilising openEO or extending openEO with new functionality or adaptations.

The following list contains proposals for possible features or extensions for openEO. The participants could either work on their own ideas or implement one of the proposals:

- **OpenID Connect Integration** - OpenID Connect is a mechanism to authenticate and authorise users against a service provider. openEO uses this protocol, however, it has not been implemented at back-or front-ends.

- **Process Graph Storage** - Develop the possibility to store process graphs by implementing the functionality on the client-side and the server-side.
- **GraphQL Wrapper** - Create a GraphQL Wrapper for openEO. GraphQL is an evolving technology that is an alternative for RESTful services. This feature investigates the feasibility of providing a GraphQL endpoint for openEO.
- **Compliance Testing** - Develop a framework that enables to test the compliance for different openEO back-ends. The framework should ensure that the requirements of openEO are met and the outcomes from different back-ends are identical.
- **GEE Back-End Extension** - Extend the GEE back-end of openEO to support other GEE scripts. Do you have any Google Earth Engine script you want to run with openEO? We may be able to add the required processes to the back-end and run your script via openEO.
- **Extensions to the Python Client**
 - **Job Management** - Implement the job management functionality in the openEO Python client.
 - **Authentication** - Add Authentication to the openEO Python client.
 - **Exception Handling** - Add Exception Handling / Error Handling (e.g. If a process is called, that is not implemented by the back-end) to the openEO Python client.
 - **Delete Files** - Add a feature to delete user files (API: /users/{user_id}/files/{path} endpoint) to the openEO Python client.
 - **User class** - Add a User class (maybe returned by session.auth()) to the openEO Python client
- **JavaScript Client** - Extending the JavaScript client library

3.6. Participants

The 24 attendees that were participating the Hackathon can be categorised into the following categories:

- Experts in the field of Remote Sensing and Geoinformatics
- Novice users with basic knowledge in Remote Sensing and Python or R programming (e.g. students)

The participants were asked to provide honest opinions regarding the usability, and to participate in the post-session wrap-up and discussions.

Furthermore, the attendees of the Hackathon were supported by mentors, who provided help and guidance, if necessary. Some mentors collaboratively worked together with the participants to develop endpoints and interfaces for the back-ends, and new features in the clients.

4. Findings

In this section the findings are listed collected during the "Test Case" session and the discussions with the participants of the Hackathon.

Generally, the overall feedback on the current implementations of the openEO clients, back-end drivers and the Core API by the participants was predominantly positive. Nearly all attendees were able to finish the test cases with no or just a few hints from the mentors. Therefore, the overall design of the basic functionality of openEO, that was tested using the test cases, was proved to be usable and understandable for users. Multiple participants stated, that they liked the availability of client libraries in different programming languages. Furthermore, the attendees positively responded that the available back-end drivers enable the easy setup of new back-ends.

The following subsections list the potential improvements for different aspects of openEO. For an insight on the overall perception on the openEO project see deliverable D08: "Preliminary User Requirements report" of the openEO project.

4.1. General

- **Insufficient documentation** - The participants of the Hackathon had problems to find certain functions or function arguments, as well as explanations for the various endpoints of the back-ends. Therefore, the documentation on the clients and Core API should be extended and improved.
- **Providing examples** - Next to the improvement of the documentation the users mentioned that they required more examples on how to use openEO. A "Cookbook" or "Notebook" approach was suggested as a visual approach to openEO by the participants.
- **Visualising process graphs** - Attendees who did not have extensive experience in programming mentioned that it could be useful to provide a visual approach to construct nested function calls in openEO, e.g. using a visual process graph builder.
- **Improve overview on state** - The users complained the missing overview of the current state of processing and the overall exception handling. A potential improvement is enhancing the transparency of the openEO processing.
- **Standardising naming** - The naming of image collections, characteristics of image collections (e.g. bands) and processes was criticised for being inconsistent, between different back-ends and clients.
- **To less features** - The users requested additional features and data sets to be integrated into openEO, as currently the available features and data sets are perceived as too sparse.
- **UDFs hard to implement** - Some participants mentioned that they had problems to integrate UDFs in their processing graphs. The users wished an improved usability to leverage the development of user-defined functions.

4.2. Core API

- **Data sets with disjoint extents** - The participants pointed out, that the openEO API specification currently only supports the specification of one extent (e.g. spatial extent or temporal extend). The need may arise to specify multiple extents to filter the data sets. Additionally, it should be possible to define open intervals.
- **Debugging and control on process flow** - There is currently no debugging of the process graphs in openEO as well as access to intermediate results and processing meta-data. The users e.g. might want to know the impacts of applied filters on the data sets. In comparison, GEE allows to get intermediate results and information using the print() function.
- **Naming of aggregate functions** - The naming of aggregation functions (e.g. min_time, max_time, mean_time) was confusing for some attendees of the Hackathon. It was proposed to standardise the naming and use more generic functions (e.g. min, max, mean).
- **Restructuring NDVI** - The participants mentioned that the NDVI process could be defined with general parameter names as "normalized_difference". Therefore, NDVI could be a shortcut without band parameters, automatically selecting suitable bands by their common names.
- **Common band names** - The names of bands are differing between products. This makes it more difficult for users to create processes, using certain bands and achieving expected results. It was mentioned to use STAC, which defines common names for bands, e.g. based on their wavelength, to provide standardised band naming. Furthermore, the naming of bands for the same products at different back-ends should be unified.
- **Further references / links for data discovery and other parts of the API** - It was suggested to make the API compatible with HATEOAS (Hypermedia), to allow adding additional meta-data information/formats to the data discovery (e.g. INSPIRE).
- **Missing API versioning** - Attendees were stating that they are missing version information of the API that is implemented by the different back-ends. The integration of versioning could improve backward compatibility and ensures stable contracts between back-ends and clients.
- **Improve error messages** - The error messages that are currently returned by the back-ends contain not enough information. The Core API should specify more useful error messages to provide guidance to the users and improve the overall usability of openEO.

4.3. Python Client

- **More choices for time ranges** - It was mentioned that it would be useful to allow providing Date or DateTime objects to the temporal filtering of the image collections, next to ISO 8601 string representations.
- **Display of ImageCollection** - A participant suggested to improve the displaying of the ImageCollection class. Currently the printing of ImageCollection objects only returns the default object string. It would be useful to return a string with the information of the used

product and the applied processes.

- **Merging similar functions** - The methods `session.image()` and `session.imagecollection()` should be merged, using the key element of the Core API "product_id".
- **Merge `session.get_collection()` and `session.imagecollection()`** - It was mentioned, that the methods `get_collection()` and `imagecollection()` of the session class have separate functionalities, as the first method returns information about the collection and the second one returns a `ImageCollection` based class.
- **Download from remote folder** - A attendee mentions that it would be useful to enable downloading a file from a remote 'folder'.
- **Adding error handling to user file handling** - Error handling to user file upload / download / deletion could be improved by adding exceptions, and more relevant return values than "true" or "false".
- **Different approach on building process graph** - A participant proposed to construct process graphs by creating a module with all processes in static functions, which returns a new combined image collection (e.g. `new_imagecollection = openeo.processes.ndvi(imagecollection.band1, imagecollection.band2)`). This approach would be more common for Python users in the remote sensing area.
- **Method for tile counting** - A method was proposed that counts the number of images with a valid mask in a time series for all bands of the input data set.
- **Add more methods for data aggregation** - Currently the Python client just supports `max_time()` and `min_time` aggregations. Additional aggregation methods like `mean_time` and `median_time` could be useful.
- **Renaming UDF methods** - It was proposed renaming the functions for the UDFs, so that the "udf" keyword is mentioned. Otherwise it may be hard to find the correct functions that apply the UDFs.
- **More information on `download()`** - Some users asked for more detailed information for the `job.download()` function.
- **Applying processes was misleading** - The application of processes was confusing for some users at the Hackathon. It was expected, that a method call (e.g. `".min_time()"`) would return meta-data information about the processes and not applying the processes to the image collection. Therefore, it was mentioned that it might be useful to introduce a separate `Process` class, to create better separation.
- **Programming style** - Some participants recognised that the 'functional' programming style used in the clients, is similar to the GEE approach. It was observed, that users who have used GEE before had less problems using the openEO clients.

4.4. R Client

- **Improve error messages** - Participants mentioned that the error messages that are returned by the R client are not very helpful. Additionally, the status codes of HTTP requests are not returned. These can be useful for the users to understand the problem.

- **Performance issue with describeCollection()** - The describeCollection() function was criticised for causing performance issues on some operating systems. Especially, on macOS with rgdal installed, it performed slow.
- **Making required packages optional** - It was mentioned that the R client heavily depends on external packages like udunits2 and cairo. Installing the R client with the external package dependencies, particularly if the user does not have root access, caused problems for some participants.

5. Implementations

The participants of the Hackathon used two hacking sessions on 25-26.06.2018 (each around 4 hours) to implement ideas using openEO. The implementations were based on own ideas or suggestions that were provided by the consortium of openEO. The attendees were asked to work in teams or individually. At the end of the hacking sessions a wrap-up was conducted in which each participants presented what they had achieved and their general insights and opinions on openEO.

The ideas that were implemented include:

- A tool to generate client libraries for openEO.
- An API wrapper for providing an endpoint for communication using openEO and GraphQL.
- Testings on using the new GDAL pixel functions to provide modular descriptive processing.
- A process graph visualiser and builder in the web-editor project of openEO.
- Providing access to Proba-V data.
- Integration of support on OpenSearch on different back-ends using GeoNetwork and pycsw.
- Improvements and extensions on User-Defined Functions (UDFs) on the GeoPySpark driver.
- Various extensions of the functionality and bug fixes for the Python client.
- Extending and Fixing issues of the R Client.

In the following sub-sections some of the ideas are presented in further detail.

5.1. Code Generation for openEO Clients

The project idea emerged from the question on how to efficiently maintain the three client implementations of openEO. Particularly: i) the need of keeping the clients in sync with the openEO Core API specification, ii) the harmonisation of the implementations across the clients, and iii) taking into account the requirements of each programming language.

Since openEO is standardised and extensively described using a Swagger 2.0 specification the project aims to automatically generate clients for different programming languages, based on the openEO Core API specification. A first test, using the Swagger Code Generator 2.4.0, lead to a vast amount of generated code and unclear implementations. Another attempt, using the Swagger Code Generator 3.0.0 likewise was not capable to solve the problem, since the availability of generators is quite limited at the moment.

The solution that was finally implemented uses Swagger Codegen with custom code generation templates, using the mustache template system. The advantage of mustache is its logic-less template syntax that can be used to describe different requirements and demands. The final state of the project enabled to generate TypeScript/JavaScript clients that utilise the [Fetch API](#).

Figure 5.1: An overview on the processing flow for generating clients using Swagger Codegen and Mustache templates.

The projects source code can be found at: [openEO GitHub - Code Generation for openEO Clients](#)

5.2. GraphQL Wrapper for openEO

The GraphQL wrapper project offers a new and state-of-the-art endpoint for accessing the REST API of openEO.

GraphQL is a modern query language for APIs. Furthermore, it provides a run time for fulfilling queries, returning responses that exactly fitting the needs of the request, without returning unnecessary data. While REST APIs typically require to request data from multiple sources, GraphQL enables to get all the data in a single request. Additionally, GraphQL uses object typing to ensure that the clients can only ask for what is possible and provides clear and helpful errors.

The project, that was developed during the Hackathon, provides a wrapper on top of the existing JavaScript client, to provide the required endpoints for GraphQL. The final state at the end of the Hackathon enables to send GraphQL queries for data and process discovery, altering data like registering a new account and subscribe to changes using GraphQL subscriptions.

The project is using the popular Apollo platform to build a GraphQL endpoint on top of existing REST APIs. The advantage is that each back-end, implementing the openEO REST API spec-

ification, can use the GraphQL wrapper to provide another access point to their service. Apollo provides a client development tool for fast and easy testing of queries.

Figure 5.2: The GraphQL editor with a sample query for multiple data sources.

The projects source code can be found at: [GraphQL Wrapper for openEO](#)

5.3. Web Editor: Visual Process Graph Builder

Multiple participants of the openEO Hackathon expressed the need for a more visual approach to create chains of processes, using openEO. Therefore, a project idea raised to implement a visual process graph builder into the existing [web editor project](#) of openEO.

The project is similar to the ArcGIS model builder and provides user-friendly access to openEO. After the user created a process graph, using the visual process graph builder, it can be sent to one of the back-ends for processing. Internally the visual process graph builder is based on JavaScript, using the block.js library.

The visual process graph builder, that is integrated into the openEO web editor, offers the opportunity to create a more visual and easy access to openEO. Furthermore, it can provide a new "selling point" for the project, to offer services to a broader audience and ease the access to the data and processes capabilities.

Figure 5.3: Screen-shot of the Visual Process Graph Builder.

The projects source code can be found at: [Web Editor: Visual Process Graph Builder](#)

5.4. GDAL Pixel Functions

The GDAL VRT driver enables to create virtual GDAL data sets that are composed of other GDAL data sets, with various transformations, altered meta-data or potentially applied algorithms. The .vrt files are saved as an XML format, containing the VRT descriptions. GDAL pixel functions were introduced with GDAL 2.2 and can be used to apply pixel functions that are written in Python or C/C++ to generate a new output raster from derived bands that are containing pixel information.

The GDAL pixel functions therefore can be used to create a descriptive virtual XML file, that contains the operations that the user wants to apply to the image collection. Subsequently, this .vrt can be used for applying an efficient one-time processing in a containerised environment. The project was created with the aim to fasten and generally improving the execution file-based back-ends that are using a container-based processing platform (e.g. OpenShift).

D10: Hackathon Report

```
--<VRTDataset rasterXSize="10980" rasterYSize="10980">
-<SRS>
  PROJCS["WGS 84 / UTM zone 33N",GEOGCS["WGS 84",DATUM["WGS_1984",SPHEROID["WGS
  84",6378137,298.257223563,AUTHORITY["EPSG","7030"]],AUTHORITY["EPSG","6326"]],PRIMEM["Greenwich"
  </SRS>
-<GeoTransform>300000.0, 10.0, 0.0, 3400020.0, 0.0, -10.0</GeoTransform>
-<VRTRasterBand band="1" dataType="Float32" subClass="VRTDerivedRasterBand">
  <PixelFunctionType>pixel_functions.process_ndvi</PixelFunctionType>
  <PixelFunctionLanguage>Python</PixelFunctionLanguage>
  -<SimpleSource>
    <SourceFilename relativeToVRT="1">/home/luca/band2.vrt</SourceFilename>
  </SimpleSource>
  -<SimpleSource>
    <SourceFilename relativeToVRT="1">/home/luca/band4.vrt</SourceFilename>
  </SimpleSource>
</VRTRasterBand>
</VRTDataset>
```


Figure 5.4: (left) A .vrt file, describing pixel functions; (right) Resulting output image

The projects source code can be found at: [GDAL Pixel Functions](#)

6. Impact

The openEO Hackathon resulted in the discovery of various usability problems and user requirements, raised through tests with potential users in real world environments. The results will be used to improve the quality of openEO, leverage the effort to fulfil user needs and provide an outstanding user experience. Most of the problems that were found during the Hackathon, were directly assigned as issues to the respective GitHub repositories. Some of the issues were furthermore resolved by participants during the "Hacking" sessions. An overview of all issues identified during the Hackathon and the subsequent discussions can be found at the [openEO Hackathon GitHub repository](#).

Another Hackathon achievement are the projects that were developed by the participants. The projects provided new insights to features extending and improving openEO and can be used to provide new functionality. Particularly, the projects that were presented in the section 5. Implementations give further insight on the improvement of openEO. Other, smaller implementations or extensions on top of openEO were applied in the Python or R clients during the Hackathon and will be published in the next releases of the clients. Issues that were not resolved yet, will be addressed in the near future. Features that were developed for the back-end drivers, will be used by the driver developers and released in cooperation with the development of the Core API and openEO clients.

Overall, the outcome of the Hackathon has a positive impact on openEO and helps to straighten the development of openEO on all levels. Therefore, the organisers of the openEO Hackathon and the openEO consortium members are considering organising an additional Hackathon after a first fully functional version of openEO is released, to get further input from potential users and investigate the user needs and requirements to the adaption of openEO.

Appendices

A. Photos of the openEO Hackathon

Figure A.1: First day of the openEO Hackathon.

Figure A.2: Presentation introducing openEO to the participants.

Figure A.3: Second day of the openEO Hackathon.

Figure A.4: Presentation of the projects of the Hackathon.

Figure A.5: Invitation flyer for the openEO Hackathon.